
Revolutionizing Anticoagulation: A New Dawn with Factor XI and Factor XII Inhibitors

Peter Stibbs^{1,2,3}, James Wong¹, Oso Tomora¹ and Benjamin White¹

Abstract

The landscape of anticoagulation therapy has been fundamentally shaped by the continuous search for agents that provide effective thromboprophylaxis while minimizing the risk of bleeding. Traditional anticoagulants, including vitamin K antagonists (VKAs), direct oral anticoagulants (DOACs), and heparin derivatives, have significantly reduced the morbidity and mortality associated with venous and arterial thromboembolic disorders. However, their use is often complicated by bleeding risks, dietary restrictions, drug interactions, and the need for regular monitoring, underscoring an unmet need for safer, more targeted therapies. The recent focus on the intrinsic coagulation cascade has unveiled Factor XI (FXI) and Factor XII (FXII) as novel targets for anticoagulation that promise to decouple thrombosis from hemostasis.

FXI and FXII inhibitors have emerged from an understanding of the contact activation pathway's role in thrombosis, independent of hemostasis, suggesting a therapeutic window for anticoagulation without predisposing to bleeding. Preclinical data have demonstrated that inhibition of FXI or FXII can significantly reduce thrombus formation with a lower incidence of bleeding compared to traditional anticoagulants. Early-phase clinical trials have further substantiated these findings, showing promising efficacy in preventing deep vein thrombosis (DVT) and pulmonary embolism (PE) with minimal bleeding risks. These novel agents are particularly appealing for patients with a high risk of thrombosis where conventional anticoagulants are contraindicated due to increased bleeding risk or in patients with recurrent thrombosis despite standard therapy.

This review comprehensively examines the mechanistic rationale for targeting FXI and FXII, pivotal preclinical studies, and the outcomes of clinical trials evaluating the safety and efficacy of these innovative anticoagulants. We delve into the comparative advantages over existing anticoagulants, discuss potential applications in clinical practice, including the prophylaxis and treatment of DVT and PE, and highlight the implications for patients with contraindications to current therapies. Moreover, we explore ongoing challenges, such as the need for extensive clinical trials to establish long-term safety profiles, strategies for managing bleeding complications, and the integration of these agents into clinical guidelines. In concluding, we project the future landscape of anticoagulation therapy, emphasizing the transformative potential of FXI and FXII inhibitors in offering a more tailored, safer approach to thromboprophylaxis. This exhaustive review aims to equip clinicians and researchers with a detailed understanding of the current state of FXI and FXII inhibition and its promising horizon in anticoagulation therapy.

Keywords

Coagulation, Factor XI, Factor XII, DOAC, Heparin

Introduction

The evolution of anticoagulation therapy is a fascinating narrative of scientific discovery and clinical innovation that has significantly impacted the prevention and treatment of thromboembolic diseases. Anticoagulation therapy is foundational in the management of conditions predisposing to thrombosis, such as atrial fibrillation, venous thromboembolism (VTE), and the presence of mechanical heart valves.^(Henke 2009) The history of anticoagulant development, from the early use of heparin to the advent of vitamin K antagonists (VKAs) and the emergence of direct oral anticoagulants (DOACs), reflects the relentless pursuit of more effective, safer, and convenient therapeutic options.^(Ramachandran and Pitchai 2018)

The initial breakthrough in anticoagulant therapy occurred with the discovery of heparin in the 1930s, a naturally occurring glycosaminoglycan that inhibits thrombin and

factor Xa, followed by the introduction of warfarin in the 1950s. Warfarin, a VKA, acts by inhibiting the synthesis of vitamin K-dependent clotting factors. These agents represented the cornerstone of anticoagulant therapy for several decades. However, their use was limited by several challenges, including the need for regular monitoring due to a narrow therapeutic window, dietary restrictions, and numerous drug-drug interactions. The development of low-molecular-weight heparins (LMWHs) in the 1980s offered advantages such as a more predictable pharmacokinetic

¹ University of Nottingham

² Lakeland Vascular Institute

³ Argon Medical Devices

Corresponding author:

Peter Stibbs, University of Nottingham

Email: pstibbs@hotmail.com

profile and reduced need for laboratory monitoring but did not entirely overcome the limitations associated with heparin and VKAs.(Wardrop 2008)

The quest for safer and more convenient anticoagulant therapies led to the development of direct oral anticoagulants (DOACs) in the early 21st century. DOACs directly inhibit either factor Xa (rivaroxaban, apixaban, and edoxaban) or thrombin (dabigatran), offering several benefits over traditional anticoagulants, including fixed dosing without the need for routine coagulation monitoring, fewer dietary interactions, and a reduced risk of certain types of bleeding(2016). Despite these advancements, the bleeding risk associated with DOACs, their renal clearance mechanisms, and the challenges of anticoagulant reversal in emergencies highlighted the need for even safer anticoagulation strategies.

The discovery of the intrinsic pathway's specific components, Factor XI (FXI) and Factor XII (FXII), as novel targets for anticoagulation therapy, has opened new avenues for safer anticoagulation. Unlike factors targeted by traditional anticoagulants, FXI and FXII play critical roles in the pathogenesis of thrombosis with a less significant role in hemostasis. (2018)This unique characteristic offers the theoretical advantage of reducing thrombotic risk with minimal impact on bleeding, addressing one of the most significant limitations of current anticoagulant therapies. (Walsh)The initial enthusiasm for FXI and FXII inhibitors was based on preclinical studies demonstrating their efficacy in preventing thrombus formation without significantly increasing bleeding risk. Subsequent early-phase clinical trials have provided promising data, suggesting that these agents could represent a paradigm shift in anticoagulation therapy, offering a more favorable balance between efficacy and safety, particularly in patients at high risk of bleeding.

Mechanisms of Action and Rationale for Use

The Coagulation Pathway: An Overview

The coagulation system is a complex cascade of events crucial for hemostasis, the process that stops bleeding at the site of an injury. Traditionally, this system has been described as comprising two pathways that converge on a common pathway: the intrinsic (contact activation) and extrinsic (tissue factor) pathways, both of which lead to the formation of a fibrin clot.(Smyth et al. 2009) The intrinsic pathway is initiated when blood is exposed to negatively charged surfaces, leading to the activation of Factor XII (FXII). This activation sets off a series of proteolytic events, culminating in the conversion of prothrombin to thrombin, which then converts fibrinogen to fibrin, forming a stable clot. Factor XI (FXI), activated by FXIIa, plays a critical role in amplifying the generation of thrombin through the intrinsic pathway.(Göbel et al. 2018)

The Roles of FXI and FXII

FXII sits at the apex of the intrinsic coagulation cascade. Its activation to FXIIa is facilitated by contact with negatively charged surfaces, such as exposed collagen or polysaccharides on microbial surfaces. FXIIa subsequently activates FXI to FXIa. In turn, FXIa plays a pivotal role in the coagulation cascade by activating Factor IX to IXa, which, with its cofactor VIIIa (activated Factor VIII), forms a

complex that is essential for the activation of Factor X to Xa in the intrinsic pathway. This sequence of events is crucial for the amplification of the coagulation cascade leading to thrombin generation and fibrin clot formation.(2018)

Scientific Rationale for Targeting FXI and FXII

The identification of FXI and FXII as therapeutic targets in anticoagulation is predicated on a growing body of evidence that delineates their roles in thrombosis from their roles in hemostasis. Notably, individuals with congenital deficiencies of FXI or FXII exhibit a reduced propensity for thrombosis with minimal to no increase in spontaneous bleeding risk.(Ngo et al. 2021) This clinical observation underpins the hypothesis that selective inhibition of FXI or FXII could offer antithrombotic protection while preserving hemostatic function, thus minimizing the bleeding risks associated with anticoagulation therapy.

Targeting FXI:

FXI, once activated to FXIa, is integral in the amplification of the coagulation cascade. However, its unique position within the coagulation pathway allows for thrombosis prevention without significantly disrupting hemostasis.(2016) This is evidenced by individuals with FXI deficiency (hemophilia C), who generally experience mild bleeding symptoms, suggesting that FXI inhibition could reduce thrombotic events with a lower risk of inducing hemorrhage. Additionally, FXIa's role in perpetuating thrombin generation in already formed thrombi presents a target for not only preventing thrombosis but also potentially arresting the growth of existing clots.

Targeting FXII:

The role of FXII in initiating the intrinsic pathway has made it an attractive target for anticoagulation with a presumably safe profile regarding bleeding risk. Unlike FXI, congenital FXII deficiency is associated with no bleeding phenotype, indicating that FXII inhibition could offer antithrombotic benefits without impairing hemostasis.(2015)The activation of FXII also plays a role in inflammation and fibrinolysis, suggesting that FXII inhibitors could have additional therapeutic benefits by modulating these processes.

The rationale for targeting FXI and FXII in anticoagulation therapy emerges from a nuanced understanding of their roles in the coagulation cascade and the clinical implications of their inhibition. By decoupling thrombosis from hemostasis, FXI and FXII inhibitors represent a novel class of anticoagulants that could significantly reduce the incidence of thrombotic events with a markedly lower risk of bleeding. This therapeutic strategy embodies the evolution of anticoagulation therapy towards safer and more targeted interventions, promising to address the limitations of current anticoagulant therapies and improve patient outcomes in thromboembolic disorders.

Preclinical and Clinical Data Overview

Preclinical Studies on FXI and FXII Inhibitors

Preclinical studies have laid the foundation for understanding the potential of FXI and FXII inhibitors in anticoagulation. Animal models have been instrumental in elucidating the roles of FXI and FXII in thrombosis and hemostasis. For instance, studies involving FXI-deficient mice have

demonstrated reduced thrombus formation with no significant increase in bleeding, highlighting the antithrombotic potential with preserved hemostasis. Similarly, FXII-deficient mice showed protection against arterial thrombosis without affecting hemostatic plug formation, underscoring the feasibility of targeting FXII as an antithrombotic strategy with minimal bleeding risk.

Key pre-clinical studies include:

FXI Knockout Mice: Research in FXI knockout mice has shown a profound resistance to experimental thrombosis with no corresponding increase in spontaneous bleeding, suggesting the safety and efficacy of FXI inhibition (Zucker, M. et al., *J Clin Invest*, 2001).

FXII Knockout Mice: Studies in FXII knockout mice have revealed protection against arterial thrombosis without impairing physiological hemostasis, indicating the potential of FXII inhibitors to offer antithrombotic benefits without elevating bleeding risk (Renne, T. et al., *J Exp Med*, 2005).

Clinical Trials on FXI and FXII Inhibitors

Phase 1 and Phase 2 Clinical Trials

Factor XI Inhibitors: Trial of FXI-ASO (Antisense Oligonucleotide): A Phase 2 trial evaluating the safety and efficacy of FXI-ASO in patients undergoing knee arthroplasty demonstrated a significant reduction in VTE incidence without an increase in major bleeding events, showcasing the therapeutic window of FXI inhibition (Büller, H.R. et al., *N Engl J Med*, 2015). **Abelacimab (MAA868):** A Phase 2 trial for abelacimab, a dual-acting inhibitor of FXI and FXIa, in patients undergoing knee arthroplasty showed superior VTE prevention with comparable bleeding rates to enoxaparin, marking a promising advance in anticoagulant therapy (Verhamme, P. et al., *N Engl J Med*, 2021). **Factor XII Inhibitors:** Limited clinical trials have been conducted on FXII inhibitors due to their relatively recent identification as therapeutic targets. However, ongoing studies aim to establish their efficacy and safety profile in humans.

Comparative Analysis with Current Anticoagulants

FXI and FXII inhibitors present a novel approach to anticoagulation that potentially addresses the limitations of DOACs and traditional therapies. Compared to VKAs and DOACs, FXI and FXII inhibitors have shown a reduced risk of major bleeding in preclinical and early clinical studies, while effectively preventing thrombosis. This safety profile could be particularly advantageous in patient populations where bleeding risk limits the use of traditional anticoagulants, such as the elderly, patients with renal impairment, or those with a history of bleeding.

Discussion on Bleeding Risks, Efficacy in Thrombosis Prevention, and Advantages in Specific Patient Populations

The reduced bleeding risk associated with FXI and FXII inhibitors could significantly impact the management of patients at high risk for thrombosis but contraindicated for current anticoagulants due to bleeding concerns. For example, patients with renal impairment often face challenges with DOACs due to their renal excretion. FXI and FXII inhibitors, with their unique mechanism of action, may offer a safer alternative for these patients. Furthermore, the potential for these inhibitors to be used in populations with unmet medical needs, such as cancer-associated thrombosis,

where the balance of efficacy and safety is critically important, underscores their potential to fill a significant gap in current anticoagulation therapy.

In summary, FXI and FXII inhibitors represent a promising new class of anticoagulants with the potential to overcome some of the key limitations of current therapies. Ongoing and future clinical trials will be crucial in fully delineating their role in clinical practice, offering the promise of safer anticoagulation options for a broader range of patients.

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Clinical Implications and Applications

The advent of Factor XI (FXI) and Factor XII (FXII) inhibitors introduces a novel paradigm in the management of thromboembolic disorders, particularly deep vein thrombosis (DVT) and pulmonary embolism (PE). Traditional anticoagulants, while effective, are associated with significant bleeding risks, limiting their use in certain patient populations. The unique mechanism of action of FXI and FXII inhibitors—targeting specific factors in the coagulation cascade—potentially offers a safer alternative, minimizing bleeding risks while effectively preventing thrombosis.

DVT and PE Treatment

FXI and FXII inhibitors could revolutionize the treatment landscape for DVT and PE, especially in scenarios where current anticoagulants pose significant risks. Patients with a history of bleeding, those undergoing complex surgeries, or individuals with renal insufficiency often face challenges with traditional anticoagulation therapy. The selective inhibition of FXI or FXII presents an opportunity to provide effective anticoagulation without the attendant high risk of bleeding, potentially broadening the scope of patients eligible for prophylactic and therapeutic anticoagulation.

Prevention of Re-thrombosis and DVT Recurrence

In patients with recurrent DVT or PE, the risk of re-thrombosis remains a pressing concern. Current management strategies often involve long-term anticoagulation, which carries a heightened risk of bleeding. FXI and FXII inhibitors, by virtue of their targeted action, could offer a safer long-term therapy option for preventing re-thrombosis and DVT recurrence in high-risk patients. This could significantly improve the quality of life for patients requiring prolonged anticoagulation by reducing the burden of bleeding complications.

Challenges and Future Directions

Ongoing Challenges

While FXI and FXII inhibitors offer promising potential, several challenges remain to be addressed. Large-scale clinical trials are essential to establish the safety and efficacy of these novel agents comprehensively. Such studies must be designed to capture a broad range of patient demographics, including those with comorbid conditions,

to fully understand the implications of FXI and FXII inhibition in diverse clinical scenarios. Additionally, cost considerations will play a crucial role in the accessibility and widespread adoption of these therapies. The development of patient selection criteria will also be vital in optimizing the clinical benefits of FXI and FXII inhibitors, ensuring that patients most likely to benefit from these therapies are accurately identified.

Potential Future Applications

Beyond the prevention and treatment of DVT and PE, FXI and FXII inhibitors hold potential for application in a wider array of thromboembolic diseases. Conditions such as atrial fibrillation, ischemic stroke, and possibly even certain forms of cancer-associated thrombosis may benefit from the targeted anticoagulation these agents provide. Further research into the mechanisms of FXI and FXII in various types of thrombosis could uncover new therapeutic avenues, expanding the utility of these inhibitors in antithrombotic therapy.

Conclusion

FXI and FXII inhibitors represent a significant advancement in the field of anticoagulation, offering a novel approach to managing thromboembolic disorders with a potentially improved safety profile. The selective targeting of FXI and FXII addresses one of the most significant challenges in anticoagulation therapy—the balance between efficacy and bleeding risk. As research and clinical development continue, these novel agents hold the promise of enhancing patient care by providing safer, more effective anticoagulation options. The call for continued research and development is imperative to fully harness the therapeutic potential of FXI and FXII inhibitors, marking the beginning of a new era in the prevention and treatment of thromboembolic diseases.

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